

COLLEGE STUDENTS LEVEL OF AWARENESS TOWARDS CADBURY & NESTLE BAR CHOCOLATES

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Abstract:

"Marketing starts and ends with consumer". In olden days peoples celebrated the important functions with sweets and confectionaries. Important events like birthday, wedding day, school and college days or any other celebrations is started with a branded chocolates. In the olden days there were unorganized industries to make chocolates like homemade chocolates. Among all customers college students play a vital role in buying chocolates. Many companies had variety of chocolates with different flavors, size, price, quality, etc. There are innumerable companies making and selling chocolates of them these two companies play a dominant role in the industry .that is why products of these two brands are taken into consideration. The present study is focused on college students level of awareness towards Cadbury and nestle bar chocolates, it is found that majority of the college students prefer dairy milk, silk and five star chocolates from Cadbury products and kit Kat, munch, milky bar chocolates from nestle products. Sample college students often like to have chocolates with good flavor, quality hard form.

Key Words: Customer Awareness, Preference, Cadbury & Nestle Bar Chocolates

Introduction:

"Marketing starts and ends with consumer". In olden days peoples celebrated the important functions with sweets and confectionaries. It was just like sugar, but in the modern days our youngsters celebrate the functions with chocolates instead of sweets and confectionaries. Chocolates occupy a pivotal role in the industry. Important events like birthday, wedding day, school and college days or any other celebrations is started with a branded chocolates. In the olden days there were unorganized industries to make chocolates like homemade chocolates. But when days passed many companies core with variety of chocolates to attract the customers in India there are plenty of companies to make and market chocolate. It does not mean kids alone would like to taste chocolates. Nowadays people even at the 80 & 90 are interested in tasting chocolates. Still college students maintain a difference in the universe to prefer and taste chocolates.

Review of Literature:

Ankita Singh (2012) made a study on "Brand Image Measurement towards Cadbury Dairy Milk". The main objective of the study is to increase the consumption and encourage the usage of CPM as an integral part of sweets. Primary data are collected through interview method with the sample size of 140 respondents. Tools like BAV analysis were used for this study. The outcome of the study reveals that CPM is a universally accepted brand that instigates a childlike behavior and happiness among all the age groups.

Poateek Pawar (2016) conducted a study entitled "Consumer Behavior towards Dairy Milk Chocolates". The main objective of the study is to study the consumer behavior towards chocolates with reference to dairy milk and to understand the buying pattern of the consumers of dairy milk. The study involves both primary and secondary data. The primary data were collected through questionnaire with the sample size of 100 respondents by using simple random convenience sampling method. The outcome of the study reveals that the consumers are satisfied with the product. Consumers are also pleased for the sugar free chocolates because they want a product to be more benefit to them as well as concerned about the health.

Karthikeyan (2017) conducted a research, consumer satisfaction towards dairy milk chocolate. Need for the study is to find satisfaction level of customer towards dairy milk. By adopting random sampling method primary data were collected through questionnaire with 100 respondents. The finding of the study include that overall satisfaction level among the customers is more than 40%.

Statement of the Problem:

In the competitive world each and every day the consumer attitude and thoughts may change to prefer the product for our comfortable using's. It depends on price, quality, taste, flavor, brand and image, competitive products, attractiveness, and varieties etc. many times the consumer cannot identify the reasons for his satisfaction due to the problems of price change and reducing the quantities, competitive products, quality of product and purchasing behavior of products. This study make an attempts to focus on college student's awareness towards Cadbury and nestle bar chocolates. This study aims to analyze the questions given below:

- ✓ How do the college students come to know the arrival and availability if various branded chocolates?
- ✓ Which brand chocolates is preferred most by college students while purchasing bar chocolates?
- ✓ What is the status and impact of the students to take the decision for choosing and purchasing the Cadbury & nestle bar chocolates?

Objectives of the Study:

The following are the broad objectives of the study:

- ✓ To know about the level of awareness among college students towards Cadbury & nestle bar chocolates.

Methodology:

The present study is based on the primary data. The required primary data are collected through well structured questionnaires issued to 250 college students of them 29 questionnaires are found to unsuitable hence the final sample size is 221. secondary data are collected through website, magazines, etc. framework of analysis the data collected were analyzed with the help of statistical tools like simple percentage and chi-square test.

Findings:

Socio-Economic Profile of the Sample Respondents:

The Following Table1 explain about the Personal Information of the selected respondents

Table 1

Personal Profile	Number of Respondent	Percentage
Area of Residence		
Semi-urban	83	37.56
Rural	138	62.44
Age		
17 years-20 years	171	77.38
22 years-23 years	39	17.64
24 years-26 years	11	4.98
Gender		
Male	64	28.96
Female	154	69.68
Educational Qualification		
Under graduate	172	77.82
Post graduate	37	16.74
professional	12	5.43
Occupation of the Parents		
Agriculture	83	37.56
Business	31	14.02
Salaried	93	42.08
Professional	10	4.52
Retired	2	0.90
House wife	2	0.90
Marital Status		
Married	11	4.98
Unmarried	210	95.02
Type of Family		
Joint	45	20.36
Nuclear	176	79.64
Number of Members in the Family		
Up to 3	39	17.65
4	129	58.37
5	30	13.58
Above 5	23	10.40
Pocket Money Per Month		
Up to Rs.500	177	80.09
Rs.501-Rs. 1,000	22	9.95
Rs.1,001-Rs.1,500	11	4.98
Above Rs.1,500	11	4.98

Source: Primary Data

Majority 138 (62.4%) customers belong to rural area. Most of the students belong to the Age group of 17-20 years. Majority 154 (71%) customers are female customer. Majority 172 (77.8%) of them are doing ug level. The parents of most 93(42.1%) of the students are salaried employees. Majority 210 (95%) customers are

unmarried. Majority 176 (79.6%) customers are from nuclear family. Majority 129 (58.4%) are having 4 members in their family. Majority 177 (80%) customers are receiving pocket money up to Rs. 500 per month.

Determinants of Level of Awareness:

Chi square test has been applied to find out the association between selected personal profiles and awareness index about Cadbury & nestle bar chocolates:

The results are presented in the following paragraph

H₀=personal profile does not influence with level of awareness

Table 2: Association between personal profile and awareness towards Cadbury & nestle bar chocolates

Personal Profile	Calculated Chi Square Value	Table Value@5% Level	Significant/ Insignificant	Hypothesis Accept/Reject
Area of residence	0.618	5.991	Insignificant	Accept
Age	5.338	9.448	Insignificant	Accept
Gender	0.714	5.991	Insignificant	Accept
Educational qualification	3.643	9.448	Insignificant	Accept
Occupation of parents	21.23	18.30	Insignificant	Accept
Marital status	1.150	5.991	Insignificant	Accept
Type of family	8.069	5.991	Significant	Reject
Number of members in the family	3.852	12.592	Insignificant	Accept
Pocket money	18.569	12.592	Significant	Reject

Source: Primary Data

The above table 2 reveals that there is a significant association between Type of family and level of awareness, pocket money and level of awareness. Insignificant association is found among Area of residence, Age, Gender, Educational qualification, Occupation, Marital status, Number of members in the family and level of awareness. Chi square test has been employed to find out the association between personal profiles and awareness towards features of Cadbury & nestle bar chocolates:

H₀=personal profile does not influence with level of awareness

Table 3: Association between personal profile and awareness towards feature of Cadbury & nestle bar chocolates

Personal Profile	Calculated Chi Square Value	Table Value@5% Level	Significant / Insignificant	Hypothesis Accept/Reject
Area of residence	5.444	5.991	Insignificant	Accept
Age	6.658	9.448	Insignificant	Accept
Gender	2.814	5.991	Insignificant	Accept
Educational qualification	11.178	9.448	Significant	Reject
Occupation of parents	12.756	18.307	Insignificant	Accept
Marital status	0.576	5.991	Insignificant	Accept
Type of family	7.726	5.991	Significant	Reject
Number of members in the family	7.708	12.592	Insignificant	Accept
Pocket money	4.651	12.592	Insignificant	Accept

Source: Primary Data

The above table 2 shows that there is an association between Educational qualification and Type of family. Insignificant association is found among Area of residence, Age, Gender, Occupation, Marital status, Number of members in the family, pocket money and level of awareness.

Suggestion:

Suggestions to Customers:

- ✓ Customers must read the information given in the label.
- ✓ They should know the promotional offers and discounts of chocolates.

Suggestions to Merchants:

- ✓ In most of the shops chocolates are kept at showcases but it is suggested to keep the chocolates in refrigerator so that chocolates will not melt.
- ✓ They should maintain stock of most demanded bar chocolates.

Suggestions to Manufactures:

- ✓ Company should concentrate more on the advertisement new chocolates varieties.
- ✓ All varieties must be made available in all areas.

Conclusion:

The present study is focused on college students level of awareness towards Cadbury and nestle bar chocolates, it is found that window display in the departmental stores, cinema theaters etc and advertisements is

TV and cinema halls can enrich the level of awareness among college students advertisements in social media like facebook, youtube, etc., can also enhance level of awareness above the popular branded chocolates.

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